

Synthesis and characterization of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of N,O-mixed donor macrocycles derived from α -diketones and 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane

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Abstract : Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of the type [MLCl₂] (M = Ni and Zn) and [CuL(NO₃)₂] (L = 17-membered N₂O₃ macrocycle) have been synthesized by [1+1] cyclocondensation of 1,13-diaminotrioxatridecane with α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione and 3,4-hexanedione in the presence of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductances, UV-Vis, IR, ¹H NMR and FAB mass spectral studies.

Keywords : Nickel, copper, zinc, α -diketones, macrocyclic complexes.

Introduction

Oxaazamacrocyclic complexes of transition metals have been studied due to their biological and catalytic activities¹⁻⁴. Deber *et al.*⁵ have synthesized Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of dioxadiazamacrocycles derived from 1,4-bis-(2'-formylphenyl)-1,4-dioxabutane and 2,2'-ethylenedioxydiethylamine. Feng *et al.*⁶ have investigated the protonation and coordination behaviour of the trioxadiazamacrocycles derived from different linear amines and 4,6-dibenzofuranedicarbaldehyde. Earlier, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 12-membered dioxadiazamacrocycles^{7,8} and 18-membered trioxadiazamacrocycles⁹ have been synthesized in our laboratories. In the present paper, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 17-membered trioxadiazamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione and 3,4-hexanedione are described.

Experimental

NiCl₂.6H₂O (Merck), Cu(NO₃)₂.3H₂O (Merck) and ZnCl₂ (Merck) were of AR grade. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (Aldrich), 2,3-butanedione (Aldrich), 2,3-pentanedione (Fluka), 2,3-hexanedione (Merck) and 3,4-hexanedione (Aldrich) were used as such. *n*-Butanol (Sisco) and DMSO were distilled before use.

Analytical methods : Ni, Cu and Zn were determined by standard methods¹⁰. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were determined by Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-304. The IR spectra (KBr) in the region 400-4000 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 KV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ on a JEOL AL-300 spectrometer at 300 MHz using TMS as a reference.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : NiCl₂.6H₂O (0.852 g, 4.0 mmol) was dissolved in ~20 ml of *n*-butanol with stirring. The butanoic solution of 2,3-butanedione (0.315 g, 4.0 mmol) was added dropwise. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (0.789 g, 4.0 mmol in 20 ml of *n*-butanol) was added with constant stirring. The contents were refluxed for ~6 h. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, Ni^{II} complexes of other oxaazamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione and 3,4-hexanedione were synthesized. The Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of oxaazamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α -diketones such as 2,3-

butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione and 3,4-hexanedione were also prepared by similar procedure.

Results and discussion

The reactions of $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and ZnCl_2 with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and α -diketones such as 2,3-butanedione, 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione and 3,4-hexanedione in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 17-membered oxazamacrocycles (Schemes 1 and 2). The resulting complexes of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}

are green, blue and white solids respectively. These are stable at room temperature and decompose at higher temperatures. The complexes are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile and DMF but are soluble in DMSO. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Molar conductances : Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solutions in DMSO of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of oxazamacrocycles are observed in the range $52\text{--}70 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating them to be 1 : 2 electrolytes. Thus, the chloro and nitrate groups of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} .

Scheme 2. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II}

respectively which are coordinated in solid state are displaced in solution by the solvent molecules¹¹. Molar conductances of 10⁻³ solutions of Zn^{II} complexes in DMSO are found in the range 15–22 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ indicating them to be non-electrolytes. Thus the chloro groups are coordinated to give tetrahedral geometry as the ether-oxygens do not coordinate¹².

Infrared spectra : IR spectra of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes exhibit a strong band at 1550–1610 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to ν(C=N). Sharma *et al.*¹³ have reported the absorption bands at 1580–1630 cm⁻¹ due to the coordinated ν(C=N) moiety. Chandra and Kumar¹⁴ also reported the absorption bands in the region 1593–1610 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C=N) linkage in the Co^{II} and Mn^{II} com-

plexes with 12, 14, 15 and 18-membered N₄, N₂O₂, N₂O₂S and N₆ donor macrocycles. The absence of absorption bands at 3200–3400 cm⁻¹ in the complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} confirms the condensation of C=O groups of ketone and NH₂ groups of amine¹⁵. The absorption band at 1485 cm⁻¹ in Cu^{II} complexes confirms that one of the nitrate groups is coordinated with the metal ion¹⁶

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes exhibit bands in the region 16650–16950 cm⁻¹ and 26313–27771 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(P) transitions respectively indicating distorted octahedral geometry with D_{4h} symmetry¹⁷. The Cu^{II} complexes exhibit a broad band in the region 16113–16950 cm⁻¹ indicating distorted octahedral

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of oxazamacrocycles of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}

Complex	Colour	Yield (%)	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analyses (%) :		Molar conductances (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	IR ν(C=N) (cm ⁻¹)
				Found (Calcd.)			
				M	N		
C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ NiCl ₂	Green	60	202	14.42 (14.67)	6.80 (7.00)	52	1583
C ₁₅ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ NiCl ₂	Green	70	203	14.08 (14.20)	6.69 (6.80)	58	1591
C ₁₆ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ NiCl ₂	Green	63	208	13.58 (13.71)	6.38 (6.50)	62	1589
C ₁₆ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ NiCl ₂	Green	64	208	13.57 (13.71)	6.43 (6.50)	62	1589
C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₉ Cu	Blue	58	205	13.79 (13.90)	12.01 (12.20)	56	1598
C ₁₅ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₉ Cu	Blue	45	210	13.32 (13.50)	11.81 (11.90)	64	1603
C ₁₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₉ Cu	Blue	63	213	12.88 (13.10)	11.39 (11.50)	68	1599
C ₁₆ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₉ Cu	Blue	55	215	12.98 (13.10)	11.41 (11.50)	68	1599
C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ZnCl ₂	White	59	219	15.96 (16.05)	6.78 (6.89)	16	1605
C ₁₅ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ ZnCl ₂	White	65	221	15.37 (15.50)	6.59 (6.65)	18	1601
C ₁₆ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ ZnCl ₂	White	48	227	14.93 (15.01)	6.32 (6.40)	21	1609
C ₁₆ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₃ ZnCl ₂	White	51	228	14.81 (15.01)	6.29 (6.40)	22	1610

geometry due to Jahn-Teller distortion. This distortion leads to elongation of two bonds giving four short and two long Cu-L distances¹⁸.

¹H NMR spectra : ¹H NMR spectrum of Zn^{II} complex [Zn{(Me)(Pr)[17]dieneN₂O₃}Cl₂] has been recorded. A peak in the region δ 2.52 ppm is observed due to the residual methyl protons of the solvent DMSO. Free diamine shows a peak at δ 1.45 ppm due to -NH₂ protons, which disappears in the macrocyclic complexes confirming the condensation of -NH₂ groups of amine with C=O groups of ketone to give macrocycles having C=N linkages. In 1,2,8,9-tetraphenyl-3,7-diazaduohepta-2,7-diene-1,9-dione (KIM, Fig. 1) α-CH₂ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.64 ppm and β-CH₂ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm.

The free macrocycles, though not isolated, would have exhibited these resonances at almost similar position as in

KIM

Fig. 1

KIM. In the present complex (Fig. 2), the peak due to α-CH₂ protons appears at high field (δ 2.66 ppm) which supports the coordination of nitrogen atoms to the metal atom. The peak due to -OCH₂ protons remains unaffected

(δ 2.84 ppm) indicating that the oxygen atoms do not participate in coordination. In free 2,3-hexanedione ($\text{CH}_3^{\text{d}}\text{COCOCH}_2^{\text{c}}\text{CH}_2^{\text{b}}\text{CH}_3^{\text{a}}$), CH_3^{a} protons exhibit a triplet at δ 1.05 ppm, CH_3^{d} protons appear as a singlet at δ 2.35 ppm, CH_2^{b} protons as a multiplet at δ 1.12 ppm and CH_2^{c} protons as a triplet at δ 2.72 ppm. In the complex, CH_3^{d} protons of the ketone moiety give rise a singlet at δ 1.21 ppm and CH_2^{c} protons appear as a triplet at δ 1.37 ppm. These protons are at higher field as compared to the ketone supporting the coordination of C=N group with metal atom. However, CH_3^{a} protons are not affected much by coordination as these are away from the C=N group and appear as a triplet at δ 0.84 ppm. Similarly, CH_2^{b} protons of ketone moiety and β - CH_2 protons of amine residue are also not affected and appear as a multiplet at δ 1.28 ppm. Ansell *et al.*¹⁹ have reported the X-ray crystal structure of 6,7,8,13,14,15,16,17,18,19-decahydro-5*H*-[*e,n*]-8,12-diaza-1,4-dioxacyclopentadecine-iodozinc(II) iodide which shows a distorted tetrahedral coordination around Zn^{II}. It has been established that both

iodine atoms and both nitrogen atoms coordinate to Zn while ether oxygens remain uncoordinated.

Fig. 2

FAB mass spectra : The FAB mass spectra of two Ni^{II} complexes Ni{Me₂[17]dieneN₂O₃}Cl}Cl and [Ni{(Et)(Me)[17]dieneN₂O₃}Cl}Cl and two Cu^{II} complexes [Cu{(Et)(Me)[17]dieneN₂O₃}(NO₃)](NO₃) and [Cu{Me-(Pr)[17]dieneN₂O₃}(NO₃)](NO₃) and one Zn^{II} complex [Zn{Me₂[17]dieneN₂O₃}Cl₂] have been recorded using NBA matrix. The *m/z* values and the relative abundances of various fragments are given in Table 2. Peaks at *m/z*

Table 2. *m/z* Values and % relative intensities of important peaks in FAB mass spectra of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of macrocycles

Fragment	[Ni{Me ₂ [17]-dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl}Cl] (%)	[Ni{(Et)(Me)[17]-dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl}Cl] (%)	[Cu{(Et)(Me)[17]-dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) (%)	[Cu{Me-(Pr)[17]-dieneN ₂ O ₃ }(NO ₃)](NO ₃) (%)	[Zn{(Et)(Me)-[17]diene-N ₂ O ₃ }Cl ₂] (%)
[M] ⁺	8.8	21.1	5.3	6.6	8.8
[M+H] ⁺	1.0	5.3	1.8	1.3	1.8
[M-2Cl] ⁺	21.1	15.8	-	-	15.8
[M-2(NO ₃) ₂] ⁺	-	-	26.3	21.1	-
[L] ⁺	5.3	10.5	21.1	15.8	5.3
[L+H] ⁺	2.6	1.0	1.1	10.5	2.6
[L-CH ₃] ⁺	15.8	5.3	10.5	2.6	5.3
[L-2(CH ₃)] ⁺	10.5	-	-	-	10.5
[L-CH ₂ CH ₃] ⁺	-	1.0	5.3	5.3	-
[L-CH ₂ CH ₃ -CH ₃] ⁺	-	5.3	5.3	-	-
[L-CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃] ⁺	-	-	-	5.3	-
[L-CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ -CH ₃] ⁺	-	-	-	10.5	-
[M-2Cl-CH ₃] ⁺	18.4	10.5	-	-	26.3
[M-2(NO ₃)-CH ₃] ⁺	-	-	15.8	15.8	-
[M-2Cl-2(CH ₃)] ⁺	21.1	-	-	-	15.8
[M-2Cl-CH ₂ CH ₃] ⁺	-	7.9	-	-	-
[M-2(NO ₃)-CH ₂ CH ₃] ⁺	-	-	13.2	26.3	-
[M-2Cl-CH ₂ CH ₃ -CH ₃] ⁺	-	16.8	-	-	-
[M-2(NO ₃)-CH ₂ CH ₃ -CH ₃] ⁺	-	-	10.5	-	-
[M-2(NO ₃)-CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃] ⁺	-	-	-	18.4	-
[M-2(NO ₃)-CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ -CH ₃] ⁺	-	-	-	10.5	-

Scheme 3. Fragmentation pattern of $[Ni\{Me_2[17]dieneN_2O_3\}Cl]Cl$.

Table 3. Calculations of relative abundances of molecular ion [M]⁺ C₁₄H₂₆N₂O₃NiCl₂ due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion^a

Sl. no.	Ion composition	<i>m/z</i>	Fractional abundances		Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
1.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁵⁸ Ni ³⁵ Cl ₂	398	(0.68)(0.76) ² = 0.393	0.393	98.7	8.7
2.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁵⁸ Ni ³⁵ Cl ³⁷ Cl	400	(0.68)(0.76)(0.24) × 2 = 0.248	} = 0.398	100	8.8
3.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁰ Ni ³⁵ Cl ₂	400	(0.26)(0.76) ² = 0.15			
4.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁵⁸ Ni ³⁷ Cl ₂	402	(0.68)(0.24) ² = 0.039	} = 0.134	33.7	2.9
5.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁰ Ni ³⁵ Cl ³⁷ Cl	402	(0.26)(0.76)(0.24) × 2 = 0.095			
6.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁰ Ni ³⁷ Cl ₂	404	(0.26)(0.24) ² = 0.015	0.015	3.8	0.3

Table 4. Calculations of relative abundances of various fragments due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion^a

Sl. no.	Ion composition	<i>m/z</i>	Fractional abundances		Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
A : Fragment [C₁₄H₂₆N₂O₃NiCl]						
1.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁵⁸ Ni ³⁵ Cl	363	(0.68)(0.76) = 0.517	0.517	100	15.8
2.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁵⁸ Ni ³⁷ Cl	365	(0.68)(0.24) = 0.163	} = 0.361	69.8	11.0
3.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁰ Ni ³⁵ Cl	365	(0.26)(0.76) = 0.198			
4.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁰ Ni ³⁷ Cl ₂	367	(0.26)(0.24) = 0.062	0.062	11.9	1.83
B : Fragment [C₁₄H₂₆N₂O₃Ni]						
1.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁵⁸ Ni	328	0.68		100	21.1
2.	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁰ Ni	330	0.26		38	8.0
C : Fragment [C₁₃H₂₃N₂O₃Ni]						
1.	C ₁₃ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₃ ⁵⁸ Ni	313	0.68		100	18.4
2.	C ₁₃ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁰ Ni	315	0.26		38	6.9
D : Fragment [C₁₂H₂₀N₂O₃Ni]						
1.	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ ⁵⁸ Ni	298	0.68		100	21.1
2.	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁰ Ni	300	0.26		38	8

^a(a_A.^xA + b_A.^yA + c_A.^zA +)ⁿ (a_B.^xB + b_B.^yB + c_B.^zB +)^m....., where a_A, b_A, c_A etc. are the fractional abundances of the isotopes ^xA, ^yA, ^zA of element A and n is the number of atoms of A present in the ion; similarly for m atoms of B and so on.

136, 137, 154, 280, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. All the complexes show peaks corresponding to molecular ion [M]⁺ and free macrocycle [L]⁺ which confirm the formation of macrocyclic complexes. The fragmentation pattern of the complex [Ni(Me₂[17]dieneN₂O₃)Cl]Cl has been discussed in detail (Scheme 3). The complex exhibits molecular ion [M]⁺ (a) peak at *m/z* 400 (8.8%). Fragment (b) is produced due to the loss of one chloride from molecular ion (a) and appears at *m/z* 363 (15.8%). By the loss of another chloride, peak due to fragment (c) is observed at *m/z* 328 (21.1%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of (c).

(A) : In this pathway, the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and step by step loss of two methyl groups from fragment (c) gives peaks at *m/z* 313 (18.4%) and 298 (21.1%) due to the species (d) and (e) respectively. Loss of Ni from species (e) finally gives the species (f) at *m/z* 240 (10.5%).

(B) : In this pathway, the loss of the metal ion from the fragment (c) gives a peak at 270 (5.3%) due to free macrocycle (g). Successive loss of two methyl groups from fragment (g) gives peaks at *m/z* 298 (21.1%) and 240 (10.5%) due to the species (h) and (f) respectively.

The spectrum of the complex [Ni{Me₂[17]dieneN₂O₃}]-

Cl]Cl has been analysed on the basis of isotopic abundances of different nuclei particularly those of Ni [^{58}Ni (68%) and ^{60}Ni (26%)] and Cl [^{35}Cl (76%) and ^{37}Cl (24%)]. Various isotopic peaks have been observed but only the most abundant peaks have been considered while discussing the fragmentation pattern. These isotopic peaks have been analysed on the basis of theoretical calculations (Table 3). The calculation for this complex shows the molecular ion isotopic peaks at m/z 398, 400, 402 and 404 due to the different isotopes of Ni and Cl and their relative abundances are 8.7, 8.8, 2.9 and 0.3% respectively; the peak at m/z 404 is neglected due to its low abundance. In the spectrum, the relative abundances of the peaks at m/z 398, 400 and 402 with respect to base peak are 7.0, 8.8 and 1.8% respectively which are close to the calculated values. Similar calculations for other fragments of this complex are given in Table 4. Thus the mass spectral results strongly support the formation of macrocyclic complexes.

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